

INVESTMENT PREFERENCES AND RISK LEVEL: BEHAVIOUR OF SALARIED INDIVIDUAL - WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO MANUFACTURING SECTOR, BANGALORE

Dr. SUNIL M RASHINKAR

Associate Professor, School of Management, Presidency University, Bengaluru, Karnataka, India.

PRATHIBHA V

Research Scholar, School of Management, Presidency University, Bangalore, Karnataka, India.

Abstract

Purpose: The purpose of this paper is to review the investment preferences and risk-level behaviour of salaried individuals in the manufacturing sector across Bengaluru city. **Design, Methodology, and Approach:** This paper is based on a review of research papers on the awareness level of salaried individuals in manufacturing sector. The study includes the review of factors such as financial literacy and personality traits as moderating variables to study the risk and investment behaviour of the investors in choosing the type of investments and the risk-taking capabilities. **Findings:** Based on the previous literature, the paper presents a synthesised definition of Investment preference and risk behaviours. Furthermore, with the help of existing literature, the paper tries to identify the factors influencing the investment choices of salaried individuals in the manufacturing sector. **Originality/Value:** This paper gives an overview of the various investments that an individual would prefer and the risk behaviours that they exhibit while choosing particular types of investments in accordance with various socio-economic categories.

Keywords: Investment Preference, Risk Behaviour, Salaried Individual, Manufacturing Sector

Paper type: Literature review

INTRODUCTION

In India financial products for the investors on varying needs and risk appetite are issued. In the past, traditional financial products were offered by the banks (Current Accounts, Saving Banking Accounts, Recurring Deposits, and Fixed Deposits), the Insurance companies, and the Postal Department (Recurring Deposits, National Saving Certificates, Kisan Vikas Patras). However, in recent years, with the advent of LPG of financial services, the industry has offered diverse financial products such as mutual funds, shares, derivatives, life and non-life insurance schemes (Unit Linked Investment Plans (ULIPs), precious metals such as Gold, Silver as well as provident and pension funds, and children's education plans, etc.).

Investment preferences differ from person to person, as each individual behaves differently while investing. Investment behavior of the individual is influenced by his/her own environment. With an anticipation of creating high returns over a period of time and at certain level of risk, individuals invest in different financial products. Today, a number of investment avenues are available to individuals but an individual, after a thorough study of market and according to his needs and circumstances, shall have to decide which investment avenue has to be chosen.

The present study is an attempt to analyze the investment preferences and risk behavior of salaried individual investors in manufacturing sector in Bengaluru which is, incidentally, called the “Silicon Valley of South India”.

CONCEPTS AND MEASUREMENTS

Independent Variable Present study used “Big five personality traits” (“neuroticism, extroversion conscientiousness agreeableness and openness to experience”) as independent variables. To measure personality traits a total of 23 items were chosen from preceding study conducted by **Mayfield et al. (2008)**. Among these 23 items, “5 were used to measure Neuroticism, 4 were used to measure Extraversion, 5 were used to measure Openness to experience, 4 were used to measure Agreeableness and 5 were used to measure Conscientiousness”. “These items were measured using a five-point Likert scale”. **Dependent Variable** Investment intention of individuals is used as dependent variable. Items were selected from the study directed by **Mayfield et al. (2008)**. Five questions were used to quantity “short term investment intention” in respondents and five were used to quantity “long term investment intention” in respondents. The responses of individuals were measured using a “5-point ratingscale” ranging from “strongly disagree to strongly agree with each of given statements”. Investment intention of individuals is used as dependent variable. Items were selected from the study directed by **Mayfield et al. (2008)**. Five questions were used to quantity “short term investment intention” in respondents and five were used to quantity “long term investment intention” in respondents. The responses of individuals were measured using a “5-point ratingscale” ranging from “strongly disagree to strongly agree with each of given statements”. **Moderating Variable** Financial literacy is used as moderating variable in current study. To measure financial literacy study used questionnaire developed by **Van Rooij et al. (2018)**. This questionnaire measures financial literacy in two dimensions, i.e. “basic financial literacy, and advance financial literacy”. Questionnaire used five question for basic financial literacy and eleven advanced literacy questions. “Basic financial literacy” measures individual’s awareness about “numeracy, compounding interest, inflation, time value of money and money illusion”. While Advance financial literacy measures individual’s awareness about “stock market operations, Bond, Stock, and the relationship between bond prices and interest rates” **Van Rooij et al. (2020)**. Present study only measures the one dimension of individual i.e. basic financial literacy level. Each question has “only one correct answer. By assigning one point to each correct answer study calculate an index” **Van Rooij et al. (2022)**.

A REVIEW ON MEANING OF INVESTMENT PREFERENCE

Narayana (1976) found that the most important forms of urban financial investment were bank deposits, shares and securities. Mudra - **Samir’s (2021)** work brings that the fact that the working women in urban India put aside one-fifth of their earnings as savings. According to **Ahmed (2001)** investors will be provided with adequate and reliable information so that they can make sound investment decisions. **Bandgar P.K (2018)** opines that most of the investors do not know about safety of new issues of company shares, debentures and shares bought stock exchanges. **Abhijit Dutta (2000)** observes

that the individual investors have high confidence in themselves and are not guided by the market discounted asymmetric information. **Maruthupandian.P (2016)** says that investors should remember that their active participation in the activities of the investor forum is a must. **The Indian Household Investors Survey, (2022)** registers the fact that a developing economy like India needs a growing amount of household savings to flow to corporate enterprises. Kirshnudu.Ch, B. Krishna Reddy and G. **Rama Krishna Reddy (2015)** have found out that the Investors are mostly influenced by family members while taking decisions on investment. **Sridhar (2018)** records that the majority of the respondents have invested less than one lakh. **Sunatan Khurana (2018)** observe that protection is the main purpose for taking an insurance policy. **Darshana.P (2018)** the visual and print media and training programs will help investors make well informed decisions. **Vikram.S (2021)** records that major percentage of respondents have moderate knowledge and have less exposure towards the financial market. **Kasilingam.R and Jayabal.G (2009)** observe that the funds invested in small savings schemes will yield good results, not only to individual investors but also to the nation. **Selvatharangini P.S (2019)** concludes that generally people differ in their taste and preference. **Kaboor.A (2014)** finds that financial literacy is not uniform among different groups of investors. **Mathivannan.S and Selvakumar.M (2018)** observe that the teachers are saving their money for the purpose of their children's education, marriage and other welfare expenses. **Manish Sitlani, Geeta Sharma & Bhoomi Sitlani (2016)** observe that there is no relationship between demographic variables and investment choices of occupants of financial services industry. **Suman and Warne.D.P. (2018)** ascertain that the market movements affect the investment patterns of investors in the stock market. **Alagu Pandian. V and G. Thangadurai (2018)** in their study have found that most of the investors prefer bank deposits followed by investment in gold. **Parimalakanthi. Kand Dr. M. Ashok Kumar (2016)** in their study have found that investors prefer to invest in banks to enjoying the maximum safety. Though various authors have made several studies in the above areas, considering all the observed parameters. **Gupta et al. (2018)** studied the Indian household investors' preferences, future intentions and experiences and found that bonds were regarded as an investment for the retired people but that did not have much appeal for young people. The market penetration achieved by mutual funds was found to be much lower than equity shares for all age classes. **Gupta and Jain (2018)** on the basis of an all-India survey of 1463 households found the preferences of investors among the major categories of financial assets, such as investment in shares, indirect investment through various types of mutual funds schemes, other investment types such as exchange-traded gold fund, bank fixed deposits and government savings schemes. The study provides interesting information about how the investors' attitude towards various investment types are related to their income and age, their portfolio diversification practices, and the over-all quality of market regulation as viewed by the investors themselves. **Verma (2016)** studied the effect of demographics and personality on investment choice among Indian investors and found that mutual funds were popular amongst professionals, students and the self-employed. Retirees displayed their risk aversion by not investing in mutual funds and equity shares. It was also found that higher the education, higher was the level of understanding of investment complexities.

Graduates and above in qualification preferred to invest in equity shares as well as mutual funds. **Nagpal and Bodla (2019)** studied the lifestyle characteristics of the respondents and their influence on investment preferences. The study concludes that investors' lifestyle predominantly decides the risk-taking capacity of investors. The study found that in spite of the phenomenal growth in the security market, the individual investors prefer less risky investments, viz., life insurance policies, fixed deposits with banks and post office, PPF and NSC. **Davar and Gill (2019)** investigated the underlying dimensions in the selection of different investment avenues for the households. The results of the study revealed emphasis on familiarity, satisfaction, opinion and demographic dimensions for all investment avenues. **Chitra and Sreedevi (2021)** analyzed the influence of seven personality traits—emotional stability, extraversion, risk, return, agreeability, conscientiousness and reasoning—on the choice of the investment pattern. The results of the study show that these personality traits of the investors have an impact on the individuals while taking decisions and also have a strong influence on determining the method of investment.

PERSONALITY TRAIT AND RISK BEHAVIOR

Individuals risk behavior determine their investment style **Fellner & Maciejovsky (2017)** However, numerous factors influence individual's risk behaviour such as financial knowledge **Young et al. (2016)** past experiences **Hunter & Kemp (2014)** emotions **Grable & Lytton (2013)** market volatility **Diacon (2014)** Love for money **Tang (2017)**. Personal traits **Corter & Chen (2016)**. Among personality traits, Big five (Extraversion, Neuroticism, Agreeableness, Openness to Experience, Conscientious) personality traits model is most commonly used, present study also used this model in relations in investment intention. Personality traits impact individuals spending, investment management and risk behavior **Mayfield et al. (2008)**; **Krishnan & Beena (2019)**. Study disclosed that "Extroverted people are more prone to be guided by external tangible stimulators and, consequently, take risks more impulsively than introverts" **Sadi et al. (2016)**. **Mayfield et al. (2008)** also divulged similar results for the relationship of extroverted people and investment intention, beside this, he further disclosed that Conscientious individuals take higher risks less impulsively, while individuals with openness to experience trait are higher risk taker. Another study shows that Neurotic individuals feel anxiety and scared of failure so, they also feel anxiety during risky decision making **Young et al. (2021)**.

THE MEDIATING ROLE OF RISK BEHAVIOR

Behavioral intention involves subject's readiness to involve in investment. This intention is associated with risk behavior and personal financial capabilities **Fishbein, Jaccard, Davidson, Ajzen, & Loken (2015)**. Risk behavior disclosed individual's estimation of risk. Negative behavior instigated overestimation of risk which led to lose the money-making investment opportunities **Lo, Wang, & Fang (2020)**. Investors having positive behavior tend to buy stock i.e. Ranked as high-risky investment **Keller & Siegrist (2016)**. Individuals having low risk tolerance behavior hold cash and bonds **Grable & Lytton (2013)**. **Nandan and Saurabh (2016)** directed a study and disclosed that "Risk behavior

acts as mediator between personality traits and short-term investment intentions as well as long term investment intentions of individual". **Nandan and Saurabh (2016)** further divulged that "risk behavior mediated the relationship between neuroticism and short-term investment intention, extraversion and short-term investment intention and Open ness to experience and short-term investment intentions. However, Risk behavior was not found to acts as mediator between personality traits and long-term investment intention". **Pak and Mahmood (2015)** divulged that individuals personality traits influence their risk tolerance behavior which in turn influence investment decision making.

THE MODERATING ROLE OF FINANCIAL LITERACY

Financial Literacy is the "the ability to make informed judgments and take effective decisions regarding the use and management of money" **Noctor, Stoney, & Stradling (2017)**. Financial literacy has become the phenomenon of interest for policy makers and academicians because of its relevance to financial decisions **Aren & Aydemir (2014)**. Financial literacy is important to rational investment decision and long-term financial stability. Lack of financial literacy caused individual to stay away from investment **Jureviciene & Jermakova (2016)**. Study divulged that financial literacy enable investors to manage their investment and get maximum return from investment **Lusardi & Mitchell (2020)**. **Rispens (2021)** argues that "financial literacy has real potential to change migrant behaviors" Adequate financial literacy is necessary to made rational decisions **Mandell & Klein (2019)**. Financial literacy is directly associated with financial decisions **Hilgert, Hogarth, & Beverly (2012)**. Study disclosed that increase in the level of financial literacy upsurge the possibility of someone's participation in the stock market **Lusardi & Mitchell (2018)**. Individuals having less information about the financial instruments have less willingness to participate in financial markets **Bonte & Filipiak (2019)**. Besides its significance to financial behavior, financial literacy is also relevant to risk behaviour. Risk behaviour and financial literacy are key determinant of investment decision **Kabra, Mishra, & Dash (2019)**. Study finds that individuals with lower level of financial literacy and financial experts had different perceptions about financial risk. Financial experts prefer risky areas of investment as compare to less financially literate people **Diacon (2018)**. Study revealed that individuals with less information of financial instruments, less likely to participate in financial market **Bonte & Filipiak (2016)**. **Weber and Milliman (1997)** revealed that individual with more financial awareness, less perceive the financial risk and have higher intention toward investment. Study also revealed that individual perception of risk determined their decision of holding assets. Similar results are also disclosed by another study revealed individual with financial knowledge and expertise has low risk perception and higher level of trading intention **Wanyana (2012)**.

In present study individual's personality traits are used as independent variable and their investment preference is used as dependent variable. Every personality trait has a financial risk behaviour which may impact the individuals investment intention, hence risk behaviour is recognised as mediating variable **Nandan & Saurabh (2016)**. Beside this individual with more financial awareness, less perceive the financial risk and have higher intention toward investment **Weber & Milliman (1997)**. Therefore, Financial literacy is identified as the moderating variable among the relationship of risk behaviour and

investment intention. Individuals investment intention is further categories into short term and long-term investment intention as sorts by **Mayfield et al. (2008)**.

IMPLICATIONS OF THE STUDY

This study revealed the role of the Personality Traits and Financial literacy in investment preference and Risk behavior. The results of the study suggest that financial managers and investment advisor should consider the personality traits and financial risk behavior among other factors while giving advice to them. Beside this, by providing financial literacy they can induce individuals towards investment.

Fig: Research Framework

The study found that the influence of personality traits on the investment decision is more compared to that of demographic variables. From the review of literature, it can be said that various studies on investment behavior and preferences provide a piecemeal account of investment behavior of salaried individuals. Very few studies on investment behavior have been carried out in India.

CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

Our study is the first study with the perspective of Pakistan which used integrated model combining both Financial literacy and risk behaviour to understand the investment intention among individuals having different personality traits. Secondly, it observed the role of risk behaviour between individual's personality traits and investment intention. Thirdly, this study observes, does the financial literacy moderate the relationship of risk behaviour with investment intention. To address these relations, we used "Big Five personality traits" **McCrae & Costa J (2018)** and examined the data collected from 284 students with finance background. To clear understand the intention of individuals regarding investment, study divide it into two type i.e. Short term and long term. Individuals with short term financial goals revealed "short term investment intention", while individuals

with long run financial goals revealed “long term investment intention” **Mayfield et al. (2008)**. Journal of Finance & Economics Research

Results revealed that the individuals with personality traits “Extraversion”, “Agreeableness” and “Conscientious” has positive impact on STII. These results suggest that individuals who are active, sympathy toward others, determined, and well-organized have short term financial goals and are more willing toward STII. Result also revealed that individuals with personality traits “Extraversion” and Conscientious has significant positive impact on LTII. These outcomes propose that individuals who are active, determined, and well-organized also have long term financial goals and are more willing toward LTII. These results are consistent with **Krishnan and Beena (2019)**; **Nandan and Saurabh (2016)**. Beside this, study also concluded that risk behaviour partially mediates the relationship of Personality traits with STII. However, in case of Long run Risk aversion partially mediates the relationship of “Extraversion”, “Agreeableness”, “Openness to Experience”, and “Conscientious” with LTII and fully mediate the relationship of “Neuroticism” and LTII. While exploring the moderating role of the financial literacy study revealed that Financial Literacy does not moderate the relationship of Risk aversion with STII and LTII, however, financial literacy has significant positive impact on investment intention

References

- 1) M. Weing, C. Keller & M. Siegrist, The less you know, the more you afraid of- A survey on risk perception of investment products.
- 2) R. SreePriya & P. Gurusamy., Investment Pattern of Salaried People – A Study in Coimbatore District, International journal of Scientific Research, Volume: 2, No 1, ISSN No 2277 - 8179
- 3) N. Geetha & Dr. M. Ramesh, A Study on People’s Preferences in Investment Behavior, IJEMR – Vol 1 Issue 6 - Online - ISSN 2249 – 2585
- 4) C. Elisa, G. Gloria & U. Rigoni, Risk Taking, Diversification Behavior and Financial Literacy of Individual Investors, Working Paper Series, Working Paper n. 17, ISSN: 2239- 2734.
- 5) Y. A. Jasim, Risk Tolerance of Individual Investors in an Emerging Market, Journal of Risk and Diversification, ISSN 1986-4337 Issue 2
- 6) M. Giridhari & Dr. S. D. Sathya , A Study on Investment Preferences among Urban Investors in Orissa, Prerana - Journal of Management Thoughts and Practices, Volume: 3, Issue: 1, ISSN: 0974-908X
- 7) B.B.S. Parihar & K.K... Sharma, An Empirical Study of the Investment Preferences of Salaried Employees, Technofame- A Journal of Multidisciplinary Advance Research, Vol.1 No.2, 39-48
- 8) M. C. Enrico, F. Pino & P. Pierpaolo, Individual Investor Behavior: Evidence from the Clients of a Small Credit Cooperative Bank, Working Paper version 2011
- 9) C. Inga, A. Michael & T. Barry, Behavioral Bias within the Decision Making Process, Journal of Business & Economics Research, Volume 6, Number 8
- 10) J. S. Robert, Human Behavior and the Efficiency of the Financial System, Cowles Foundation for Research in Economics, Paper No. 1172
- 11) Coval, J. D. and Shumway, T. (2005), “Do behavioural biases affect prices?” Journal of Finance 60, 2005, pp. 1– 34.
- 12) Kahneman, D., & Tversky, A. (1979), Prospect theory: An analysis of decision under risk. Econometrica,

47(2) 263- 291.

- 13) Hoje Jo and Dong Man Kim (2008), "Recent Development of Behavioral Finance", International Journal of Business Research, Vol.8, No. 2
- 14) Markowitz, H. (1952), Portfolio Selection. The Journal of Finance, 7(1), 77-91
- 15) Mittal Manish and Vyas R K (2009), "Does Irrationality in Investment Decisions Vary with Income?", The IUP Journal of Behavioral Finance, Vol.VI Nos. 1 ,pp. 26-40
- 16) Nagpal S and Bodla B S (2009), "Impact of Investors' Lifestyle on Their Investment Pattern: An Empirical Study", The IUP Journal of Behavioral Finance, Vol.VI, Nos.2 ,pp. 28-51
- 17) Nawrocki, D.(1997), "Capital Market Theory: Is it relevant to practitioners?", Journal of Financial Planning, 10(5), pp. 97-103,1997
- 18) Purohit Harsh (2004), 'Recent trends in Investor's attitude with special reference to Indore and Jaipur Cities', Popular Publications, under UGC non-assigned grant to BanasthaliUniversity, Jaipur
- 19) Qawi B Raluca (2010), "Behavioral Finance: Is Investor Psyche Driving Market Performance?", The IUP Journal of Behavioral Finance, Vol.VII, No.4, pp. 7-19
- 20) Sharpe F. William (1964), "Capital Asset Prices: A Theory of Market Equilibrium under Condition of Risk", Vol. 19, No. 3(Sep., 1964), pp. 425-442
- 21) Sultana S T (2010), "An Empirical Study of Indian Individual Investor's Behavior", Global Journal of Finance and Management ,Volume 2, Number 1 (2010), pp.19-33